

Data Use Agreement

I request access to the data collected in the digital repository of the MoMiLab Research Unit, part of the IMT School for Advanced Studies, established at Lucca, Italy (hereinafter referred to as the IMT Lucca).

By accepting this agreement, I become the [data controller](#) (as defined under the GDPR) of the data that I have access to, and am responsible that I access these data under the following terms:

1. I will comply with all relevant rules and regulations imposed by my institution and my government. This agreement never has prevalence over existing general data protection regulations that are applicable in my country.
2. I will not attempt to establish or retrieve the identity of the study participants. I will not link these data to any other database in a way that could provide identifying information. I shall not request the pseudonymisation key that would link these data to an individual's personal information, nor will I accept any additional information about individual participants under this Data Use Agreement.
3. I will not redistribute these data or share access to these data with others, unless they have independently applied and been granted access to these data, i.e., signed this Data Use Agreement. This includes individuals in my institution.
4. I will reference the specific source of the accessed data when publicly presenting any results or algorithms that benefited from their use: (a) Papers, book chapters, books, posters, oral presentations, and all other presentations of results derived from the data should acknowledge the origin of the data as follows: "Data were provided (in part) by the MoMiLab Research Unit at the IMT School for Advanced Studies, Lucca, Italy". (b) Authors of publications or presentations using the data should cite the publication describing the methods developed and used by the IMT Lucca to acquire and process the data. Specifically: Papale, Leo et al., *bioRxiv* 2019. (c) Neither the IMT Lucca, nor the researchers that provide this data will be liable for any results and/or derived data. They shall not be included as an author of publications or presentations without consent.
5. Failure to abide by these guidelines will result in termination of my privileges to access these data.

Place and date:

Name and affiliation(s):

Signature:

N.B. Send this signed agreement to: *paolo.papale* [at] *imtlucca.it* to ask for access.